

Examining co-authorship in funded social science papers from Taiwan

Huei-Ru Dong¹, Chung-Huei Kuan², and Mu-Hsuan Huang³

¹ 141646@mail.fju.edu.tw

Fu Jen Catholic University, Department of Library and Information Science, No. 510, Zhongzheng Rd., Xinzhuang Dist., New Taipei City (Taiwan)

National Taiwan University, Center for Research in Econometric Theory and Applications (CRETA), No. 1, Sec. 4, Roosevelt Rd., Taipei City (Taiwan)

² maxkuan@mail.ntust.edu.tw

National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, Graduate Institute of Patent, No. 43, Sec. 4, Keelung Rd., Taipei City (Taiwan)

³ mhhuang@ntu.edu.tw

National Taiwan University, Department of Library and Information Science, No. 1, Sec. 4, Roosevelt Rd., Taipei City (Taiwan)

National Taiwan University, Center for Research in Econometric Theory and Applications (CRETA), No. 1, Sec. 4, Roosevelt Rd., Taipei City (Taiwan)

Introduction

Funding is one of the key resources for scientific rewards. Funding is commonly awarded to scholars to support their research. (Benavente et al., 2012; Bolli & Somogyi, 2011; Tan et al., 2012; Tang et al., 2017). Co-authored papers typically present the outcomes of academic collaboration. According to Larivière et al. (2006), the number of internationally co-authored papers on the social sciences and natural sciences has risen annually. However, the number of natural science papers with international co-authors is consistently higher than the number of social science papers with international co-authors. Dong (2021) explored the characteristics of funded papers by investigating Taiwanese social science papers. The findings indicated that social science papers receive greater funding at a higher rate in Taiwan. However, studies have rarely analyzed the co-authorship of funded papers. To understand the co-authorship of funded social science papers, this study examines the co-authorship and international co-authorship of funded social science papers from Taiwan.

Methodology

This study adopted the bibliometric method to analyze article data. Papers were collected from the SSCI database in which authors indicate their affiliations in Taiwan. The publication years investigated were 2015 to 2021. This study included papers published after 2015 because the bibliography of the SSCI database does not include funding information for earlier articles (Álvarez-Bornstein et al., 2017; Clarivate, 2018). The updated date of the SSCI database at the time was July 12, 2022. A total of 32,605 papers were collected.

Funded papers

Funding information in the bibliography data was used to verify funded papers. When funding data were present in the bibliography, the paper was considered funded. When funding data were absent from the bibliography, the paper was considered nonfunded. In

our study, 18,550 papers were funded (56.89%) and 14,055 were nonfunded.

Co-authored papers

Co-authored papers were categorized by the number of authors. A paper was considered a single-authored paper if the full name column in the bibliographical data contained only one name. A paper was considered co-authored if two or more authors were listed in the full name column.

International co-authorship was determined by the country of the author's affiliation. In co-authored papers, if an author's affiliated institution was in a country other than Taiwan, the paper was considered an internationally co-authored paper.

Results

Co-authored funded papers

Figure 1 shows the distribution of papers based on the number of authors for funded papers and nonfunded papers. The number of funded papers with one or two authors was smaller than the equivalent number of nonfunded papers. Conversely, for papers with three or more authors, the number of funded papers was higher than the number of nonfunded papers. The difference in the number of papers was largest when the number of authors was between four and seven. Thus, funded papers had more co-authors than nonfunded papers, and their co-authored teams were generally larger.

Figure 1. Number of authors for funded and nonfunded social sciences papers in Taiwan.

According to Table 1, the overall co-authorship rate in the social sciences in Taiwan has increased annually since 2016, from 83.63% to 90.97%. Thus, more than 90% of social science papers in Taiwan were co-authored. The co-authorship rate of funded papers was even higher at an annual co-authorship rate of over 86%. After 2019, the co-authorship rate of funded papers surpassed 91%. However, the co-authorship rate of nonfunded papers was relatively low; the lowest rate was 80.03% in 2016, and the highest was 87.51% in 2021.

Table 1. Co-authorship rate of funded social science papers in Taiwan.

	funded papers	nonfunded papers	total papers
2015	88.4%	81.3%	84.8%
2016	87.4%	80.0%	83.6%
2017	86.6%	82.0%	84.6%
2018	89.7%	83.1%	86.8%
2019	91.4%	84.0%	88.5%
2020	92.0%	86.2%	89.7%
2021	93.2%	87.5%	91.0%

Internationally co-authored funded papers

Figure 2 presents the number of internationally co-authored funded and nonfunded papers according to the number of authors. When the number of international co-authors was two, the numbers of funded and nonfunded papers were similar. However, when the number of authors was three or more, the number of funded papers was considerably higher than the number of nonfunded papers. Therefore, the number of authors for internationally co-authored papers was higher for funded papers than nonfunded papers.

Figure 2. Number of authors for internationally co-authored funded and nonfunded papers.

A further comparison of international co-authorship rates for funded and nonfunded papers was conducted. In 2015, the international co-authorship rate of funded papers was

approximately 15%, which was slightly higher than the international co-authorship rate of nonfunded papers. After 2016, the international co-authorship rate of both funded and nonfunded papers increased annually, which indicated an increase in the prevalence of international co-authorship. However, the increase in the international co-authorship rate of funded papers was much higher than that of nonfunded papers. After 2019, the international co-authorship rate of funded papers was higher than 25%, which was higher than the domestic co-authorship rate of nonfunded papers.

Figure 3. International co-authorship rate of funded and nonfunded social science papers in Taiwan.

Conclusion

This study examines the co-authorship of funded papers in the social sciences. The number of authors for funded papers was higher than that for nonfunded papers. Moreover, the co-authorship rate of funded papers was higher than that of nonfunded papers. Regarding international co-authorship, the number of authors and the co-authorship rate of funded papers were higher than those of nonfunded papers. Additionally, the international co-authorship rate of funded papers after 2019 surpassed 25%. Therefore, funded papers are positively related to co-authorship and international co-authorship, and funding can encourage both domestic and international co-authorship. Future studies can explore the effect of co-authored funded papers and the differences between subfields in the social sciences.

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References

- Álvarez-Bornstein, B., Morillo, F., & Bordons, M. (2017). Funding acknowledgments in the Web of Science: Completeness and accuracy of collected data. *Scientometrics*, 112(3), 1793–1812.
- Benavente, J. M., Crespi, G., Figal Garone, L., & Maffioli, A. (2012). The impact of national research funds: A regression discontinuity approach to the Chilean FONDECYT. *Research Policy*, 41(8), 1461–1475.

- Bolli, T., & Somogyi, F. (2011). Do competitively acquired funds induce universities to increase productivity? *Research Policy*, 40(1), 136–147.
- Clarivate. (2018, June 27). *Web of Science Core Collection: Availability of funding data*. https://support.clarivate.com/ScientificandAcademicResearch/s/article/Web-of-Science-Core-Collection-Availability-of-funding-data?language=en_US
- Dong H.-R. (2021). Exploring the Patterns of Funded Papers in Social Science in Taiwan. *Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 19(1), 115–137.
- Larivière, V., Gingras, Y., & Archambault, É. (2006). Canadian collaboration networks: A comparative analysis of the natural sciences, social sciences and the humanities. *Scientometrics*, 68(3), 519–533.
- Tan, A. M., Zhao, S. X., & Ye, F. Y. (2012). Funds promote scientific output. *Current Science*, 102(4), 542–543.
- Tang, L., Hu, G., & Liu, W. (2017). Funding acknowledgment analysis: Queries and caveats. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(3), 790–794.